

COMPRESSION MOULDING OF SMC: COUPLING BETWEEN THE FLOW AND THE LOCAL VOID CONTENTS

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SUMMARY

During compression moulding of sheet moulding compound (SMC), voids are formed that can deteriorate the properties of the final product. Here, experimental work and CFD-simulations have been carried out in order to increase the knowledge of the SMC compression moulding behaviour which highly affects the quality of the final products. The experimental as well as the numerical results indicate that a high closure velocity creates a more uniform flow. The experimental results also indicate that a uniform flow also can be obtained at low velocities with vacuum assisted moulding.

Keywords: SMC, Vacuum assisted moulding, Voids, Coloured SMC, Simulation

INTRODUCTION

Due to excellent properties and relatively low material and manufacturing costs, the use of fibre reinforced polymer composites have increased during the latest decades. One method for large scale productions of lightweight vehicle components is compression moulding of SMC. Although the technique has been considerably improved since the 1950s when it was introduced, some further improvements need to be done. The main reason why it has not come in wider use in the vehicle industry is unsatisfactory conditions of the surface finish of parts manufactured. Vacuum assisted moulding is used in the moulding industry and recommended for class A surfaces [1]. However, vacuum assistance may deteriorate the surface appearance under some conditions. For example, in [2] the results indicated an interaction effect between vacuum and mould temperature, high vacuum and high temperature resulted in an increased size of the weld line. This work intends to enhance the knowledge of compression moulding behaviour by means of CFD-simulations and experiments, and can be divided into three parts.

Firstly, a process parameter study with factorial design methodology was applied on vacuum assisted compression moulding of a standard SMC pre-preg (5412). The altered parameters were: vacuum, pressure and temperature. With a regulator, the vacuum was altered at four levels, while the pressure and temperature was altered at two levels. Each processing setup was replicated once. In order to quantify the quality of the processed samples the area fraction of the weld lines were measured, created due to dual charges, as well as thickness difference for two locations on the moulded plates.

Secondly, a compression moulding experiment which was carried out in order to study the local relative amount of voids due to flow and vacuum assisted moulding. Here, the relative void contents were measured with a high voltage insulation test performed at multiple locations diagonally over the moulded plates.

Thirdly, the 3D flow behaviour of SMC was studied by using sheets of SMC with dissimilar colour in compression moulding. In addition, CFD-calculations were carried out for a number of initial conditions regarding temperature distribution. The model, which captures many of the rheological properties of SMC, can be of assistance during moulding tool design and pre-preg lay-up procedure to prevent deterioration of the material caused by poor flow. To validate the model, simulations were compared with the coloured SMC experiment and previous experiments [3].

METHODS AND EQUIPMENT

All compression moulding experiments have been carried out with a circular mould of diameter 32cm with a vacuum assistance capability mounted in a modified Fjellman 310 ton press with parallel closure control. The SMC prepregs used were professionally manufactured by Reichhold AS where the coloured SMC were manufactured by adding different pigments to a mutual recipe. Hence, green, white and black prepregs were obtained with equal rheological properties. Then circular prepreg sheets were made by hand with a circular cutting tool with a diameter of 15 cm, which then was placed in air sealed containers until moulding in order to prevent dry-out. The charges were prepared by randomly picking sheets from the containers. By exchanging sheets, the charges could obtain approximately equal weight. For the mouldings with coloured SMC, charges containing of 2 green, 2 white and 3 black randomly picked layers were centrally placed in the mould. The order of layers for the coloured SMC can be seen in Figure 1(a).

Figure 1. Stacking order for the coloured charges circular charges (a), placed in the centre of the mould. In (b), a side view of the dual charges with two half circles can be seen. The dual charges were made from one circular charge of diameter 15cm which was divided in half into two and then separated 5cm.

In order to achieve a measurable weld line, the charges were split into two half-circles in the first and second experimental series, see Figure 1(b). The prepared prepreg charges were then placed by hand in the moulding tool where laser lights were used to create patterns inside the moulding tool which aided fast and accurate displacement in order to minimize possible pregel effects. All charges were placed in the centre of the mould, but the dual charges were separated 5 cm.

As an indication of the local void content a high voltage insulation test was performed [2][3]. The high voltage insulation test, which is a modified version of the standard test IEC 60243-1, called the step method, was carried out at ABB Plast where samples are placed in an oil bath, squeezed between two electrodes over which a voltage is applied at a low level and that is increased every 20th second, at first by 2 kV and then by 1 kV as the expected disruptive discharge level is approached. The results have then been divided with the local plate thickness where the disruptive discharge occurred for a more adequate response given in kV/mm, independent of the thickness.

Image analysis has been carried out with the software ImageJ to quantify the flow. Images of the surfaces of the coloured plates were recorded with a regular digital system camera, while cross-sections and weld lines were scanned with a regular desktop scanner. For samples created with dual charges, the area fraction of the weld line was measured. For the coloured plates created with centred circular charge, the area fraction of green and white was measured on the top, see Figure 2, as well as the width of the green and white inner layers. In Figure 3 examples of cross-section of the outermost 5 cm can be seen. As seen, it was not possible to determine from which layer the black SMC had originated from when the layers had intersected.

Figure 2. Top side view of two samples created with the same velocity and mould temperature, but (a) without and (b) with vacuum assisted moulding. The green SMC is initially from the bottom layer.

Figure 3. Cross section of the outermost 5 cm of the same two samples as above in Figure 2, where (a) is created without vacuum assistance and (b) with vacuum assistance (75% vacuum).

The software MiniTab was used to facilitate the analysis of the experiments carried out with design of experiment methodology. Since changing the temperature of the moulding tool is time-consuming, all low temperature mouldings were carried out first, and then all at the high level which makes the design blocked. However, the experiments have nevertheless been analysed as a split plot designs in order to render the possibility to expose interaction effects with the temperature. 95% confidence intervals were utilized to determine important effects with one exception mentioned in the text. The models were set-up by first including all possible interaction up to the 3rd

order and then by removing the effect of highest order with smallest significance one at a time. Moreover, when non-significant effects were removed from the model the hierarchy principle was used, which means that non-significant main effects are remained in the model if they are involved in significant higher order interactions [7].

PROCESSING PARAMETER

The values of the design parameters are presented in Table 1. From these samples, two measurements were made, the area fraction of the weld line within a chosen control surface and the thickness difference at two locations on the plates, where point 1 was at the weld line and point 2 at the side, 10 cm from the centre, where the prepreg has flowed freely without meeting another flow front.

Table 1. Values of design parameters. The bottom surface temperature was 3° higher, in order to prevent tool damage.

Vacuum				Pressure		Temperature		Velocity
0	0,5	0,75	0,9	-1	1	-1	1	-
0%	50%	75%	90%	40bar	70bar	145°C	155°C	2,5mm/s

Individually, all altered factors are significant for the area fraction of the weld line. All parameters also contribute to interaction effects which are vacuum combined with temperature, and pressure combined with temperature. It is clear from the interaction effects plot in Figure 4(a), that the weld line size is quite small for all levels of vacuum at low temperatures. However, when the temperature is increased to the high level, the area fraction of the weld line is increased as the vacuum level is increased. The results also indicate an interaction effect between the mould temperature and the pressure level. At low temperatures, the weld line area fraction is approximately the same for both pressure levels and when the temperature level is increased to the high level, the weld line area fraction is increased for both the high and low pressure level, but noticeable more for the high pressure level.

Figure 4. In (a), the interaction effects for the weld line response can be seen where the scale to the right is the percentage of weld line in the measured area. In (b), the interaction effect between temperature and vacuum can be seen on the measured thickness difference at the two locations on the plates.

The thickness measurements revealed that every plate was thicker at point 1 (in the weld line) than at point 2. Analysis of the thickness difference between point 1 and 2 revealed one clear interaction effect between vacuum and temperature, see Figure 4(b). Moving from low to high temperature increased the thickness difference for all vacuum levels except for 90% vacuum, however, the smallest difference was obtained when the vacuum level was at 50% and the temperature was low.

VOID TRANSPORT DURING MOULDING

Initial high voltage insulation tests indicated that the amount of voids in the moulded plates varied with the flow and could be minimized with the aid of vacuum assistance. Therefore, experiments were carried out with dual charge stacking patterns moulded with or without vacuum assistance with 3 replicates, see Table 2. Then the electrical insulation properties were measured diagonally over the plates in order to give the local relative void contents. Since the exact location of the disruptive discharges could not be defined before-hand three sections were defined containing disruptive discharges located at radii of 0 – 5 cm, 5 – 10 cm and >10 cm, respectively.

Figure 5. The electrical insulation properties in kV/mm as a function of the interaction effect between vacuum and section.

Table 2. Process settings.

Vacuum	Velocity	Temperature	Pressure
0% or 75%	2,5mm/s	150bottom, 147 top	450kN

The analysis revealed that the section on the plates was a main effect affecting the insulation properties, however, the interaction effect combined with vacuum also turned out to be a significant effect, see Figure 5. As seen, the highest insulation properties can be found in section 3 which correspond to the outer part of the plates where most flow have occurred. Applying 75% vacuum, increase the insulation properties for both section 2 and 3, but reduce it in section 1 where the two flow fronts have intersected.

FLOW VISUALIZATION WITH COLOURED SMC

Here, the effects of the vacuum, closing velocity, and temperature on the final flow pattern were studied, see Table 3.

Table 3. Values of design parameters. Temperature indicate top surface, the temperature at the bottom surface was 3-4 °C higher to prevent tool damage.

Vacuum		Velocity		Temperature		Pressure
-1	1	-1	1	-1	1	-
75%	0%	2,5mm/s	10mm/s	144°C	154°C	450kN

Figure 6. The plot in (a) illustrate the interaction effects affecting the amount of green on the top from the bottom layer. (b) Illustrates the significant interactions effects for the area fraction of white on the top.

First the area fractions of green were measured for the topside. The analysis of the response reveals that vacuum is involved in interaction effects with both the ram velocity and the mould temperature, see Figure 6(a). Without vacuum assistance, the amount of green can be reduced by raising the ram velocity or the temperature. With vacuum assistance, a slower ram velocity is slightly in favour over a higher ram velocity but the temperature should be kept low in order to minimize the squish effect. Analysis of the area fraction of white for the top exposed a significant interaction between vacuum and ram velocity, see Figure 6(b). This area fraction increases with a higher ram velocity for mouldings without vacuum assistance. For vacuum assisted mouldings, the highest area fraction of white is obtained with slow ram velocity and is only slightly lowered with high ram velocity.

According to the analysis of variance, a complex three-way interaction between all factors exists for the width of the 5th green layer, which also is likely to be true, see Figure 7(a). By inspection, vacuum level seems to have the largest effect in the interaction, since the width clearly increases when vacuum is applied. The result is also dependent on the ram velocity and mould temperature. For vacuum assisted mouldings at high ram velocities, the width seems to be facilitated by a higher temperature. But, with vacuum assisted moulding at low ram velocities, the width decreases with higher

temperatures. Without vacuum assistance, the smallest width is achieved when both the temperature and ram velocity is low. The largest width lengthening without vacuum assistance is at high ram velocity at a low mould temperature.

Figure 7. In (a), presents a cube plot where the average width (mm) of the 5th layer for all settings. The interaction effect between vacuum and ram velocity for the width of the 3rd layer is illustrated in (b).

For the third layer, white, no effect was found using 95% confidence intervals. However, using 93% confidence intervals it can be shown that vacuum assistance increase the width at low ram velocities. Without vacuum assistance, a clear increase of width can be done by increasing the ram velocity, see Figure 7(b).

NUMERICAL MOULDING SIMULATION

A numerical model to study the flow of SMC during compression moulding with computational fluid dynamic (CFD) simulations has previously been developed [5]. The model uses an isotropic temperature dependent Newtonian viscosity model, fitted to experimental measurements in order to mimic the temporal pressure distribution at two spatial locations simultaneously. The viscosity model that were found to fit the experiments best were

$$\mu = 2.15 * 10^5 e^{-0.086(T-298)}$$

and where the material properties used in the model can be found in Table 4.

Table 4. Material properties for the CFD model.

Property	Value	Unit
Molar mass	7000	g*mol ⁻¹
Density	1900	kg*m ⁻³
Specific Heat Capacity	1500	J*kg ⁻¹ *K ⁻¹
Thermal Conductivity	0,8	W*m ⁻¹ *K ⁻¹
Thermal Expansivity	1,4*10 ⁻⁵	K ⁻¹

The flow is solved with a high resolution advection scheme and a second order backward Euler transient scheme. In order to minimize the calculations, the circular

shape of the mould and charge is represented by a 5 degree slice with symmetry boundary conditions, consisting of 3750 hexahedral elements. Here, the same material model was used but the boundary conditions settings were changed into more realistic conditions that resemble the real conditions for the compression moulding experiment with coloured SMC, see Table 3 for velocity and temperature settings. In order to include the initial preheating that occurs due to the time delay between displacement of charges and moulding, static simulations were carried out where initial temperature profiles were obtained that include the effect of preheating during 6 seconds for both mould temperatures. In addition, the effect on the flow of preheating the whole charge was simulated.

Figure 8. Flow behavior when the mould temperature were set to low. The closure speed is 10mm/s in (a) and 2.5mm/s in (b).

Figure 9. Flow behavior for SMC preheated to a uniform temperature of 70°C. Where (a) is moulded at 10mm/s and (b) is moulded at 2.5mm/s. The mould temperature is set to low.

The simulations did not show any significant flow front difference between the two temperature levels, therefore only results from the low temperature level will be presented here. As seen in Figure 8 the boundary conditions and preheating from the tool gives a non-symmetric shape of the front as obtained in experimental observations in [3] and shown in Figure 2(a). Heating the whole charge implies a more uniform flow as shown in Figure 9.

DISCUSSION

Since the experiments were analysed as if they were carried out with a split plot design, the results are compromised. In a perfect experiment, effects involving temperature probably would have had a little less significance. However, the significance levels obtained here have been so high that the obtained effects should at least be clear indications.

Applying vacuum seems to influence the global flow. The mechanism behind this is not fully understood but one idea is that a pressure build-up by confined air inside the closed moulding tool is prevented. This presumed effect will be studied in future work.

When utilizing vacuum assistance during moulding, high temperatures seem to affect the result in a negative manner. The reason for this may be that the styrene starts to boil.

The thickness measurements in the first experiment can be interpreted as an indication that vacuum assistance applied at low temperatures can facilitate a more uniform flow since the thickness difference was minimized with that combination.

By assuming that higher electrical insulation properties can be correlated to a lower amount of internal voids and combining the results of the void transport test and the results from coloured SMC moulding, some conclusions can be made. First, flow of the SMC facilitates void removal during compression. Second, by using vacuum assistance (75% vacuum) the void removal is increased during flow. According to the test with coloured SMC, these settings cause a more uniform flow. Hence, a uniform flow should be used in order to decrease the amount of internal voids for freely flowing SMC. However, the void transport test also indicated that the electrical insulation properties decreased in section 1 where the weld line was located when vacuum assistance was applied. We cannot, to this date find any explanation to this. However, this effect may be avoided by using different stacking patterns such as pyramid shapes.

Due to the added temperature profiles in CFD that included the effect of preheating, and the changed temperature boundary conditions, complex flow profiles were obtained. This, however, shows similar behaviour as the moulded plates with coloured SMC and previous experiments [3]. Material closest to the hotter bottom side, which also have been in contact for a longer time, starts to flow before the colder upper part. The simulations did not reveal any significant effect due to temperature level. However, the squish effect of SMC near the mould surfaces seems more significant when it starts to form much earlier in the flow for the low velocity. Hence, the simulations seem to give a more uniform flow with a higher ram velocity, as the experiments did [3]. Moreover, the uniformly preheated charge showed a very uniform flow front, which agree with [6] where a charge was preheated uniformly to 65°C by use of microwaves.

CONCLUSIONS

The compression moulding experiments revealed that the three factors vacuum, ram velocity and mould temperature affect the global mould flow behaviour. The compression moulding experiments with coloured SMC shows that high ram velocity

tends to create a more uniform flow. Moreover, they also show that by utilizing vacuum assistance during moulding, a more uniform flow can be obtained also at low ram velocities. By increasing the mould temperatures, the inner layers are allowed to stretch further, but this also increase the squish effect.

Furthermore, the results also show that the combination of vacuum assistance and high mould temperatures should be avoided especially in mouldings where undesired weld lines are expected, since the combination tends to enlarge the weld line.

The isotropic temperature dependent Newtonian viscosity model for CFD simulations seems to be able to capture the typical flow behaviour of SMC during the compression moulding phase, that occur for both SMC preheated from the mould surface and SMC uniformly preheated by microwaves.

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